

Retracted article: Students' learning styles and academic performance in Readings in Philippine History: Basis for a proposed course syllabus enhancement

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Abstract

The article entitled "*Students' learning styles and academic performance in Readings in Philippine History: Basis for a proposed course syllabus enhancement*" (Volume 4, Issue 1, December 2022, pp. 45-51) written by Adrian Ote, Margie M. Lelangge, Nobelen Joy M. Marsonia, Sheena Joy C. Pagran, Jennilyn C. Se, and Jason A. Romero has been retracted at the request of the Corresponding Author.

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